

The 12 feats of Hercules and their relation to the Emotional Intelligence and the role of ICTs in EI training and development.

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Abstract

This article is about Hercules, a hero from Greek Mythology who is considered to be the greatest of the heroes of ancient Greek mythology the most beloved and glorious throughout the world. He faced the anger of Hera which drove him mad and drove him to murder. To be led to purification, he was forced to serve his cousin Eurystheus and perform 12 labors. His efforts were a journey into the world of emotional intelligence, knowing both himself (self-awareness) and also shaping attitudes, values, and behaviors toward those around him (empathy) to reach self-realization.

Keywords. Mythology; Hercules; Sports; Symbols; Emotions; Emotional Intelligence; Self-Actualization; Purification

1. Introduction

Social and emotional learning refers to a wide range of skills that enable a person to achieve social competence [1] verbal and non-verbal attitudes and behaviors that can affect people's lives skills that are not measured by assessment tests such as critical thinking, emotion management, conflict resolution, decision making, teamwork.

The labors of Hercules are a struggle of 12 "activities" of manifestation and management of emotions that lead to self-awareness in the sense of emotional unity.

2. Hercules in Greek Mythology

Mythology is the study and interpretation of a culture's often sacred tales or myths known as myths or the collection of such stories. The word comes from the Greek myth about the history of people, and logos for the word or speech, so the oral history of the people [2].

These stories deal with various aspects of human life, telling the stories of ancestors and the origin of people and the world, such as the meaning of life and death, the afterlife, good and evil, values and traditions, and also the stories of the god or gods. Myths also describe the origin or nuances of long-standing customs or explain natural phenomena such as the rising and setting of the sun, the cycle of the moon, the seasons, thunder, and lightning.

In Greek mythology, myths explained everything from religious rituals to the weather and gave meaning to the world people saw around them [3]. They also referred to heroes with superhuman, usually god-given powers - as in the case of Hercules.

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One of the heroes of ancient Greek mythology is Herakles. The place of his birth is not specified, but Thebes is mentioned [4]. He is the son of the god Zeus and the mortal Alcmena, a powerful and fearless demigod. His name comes from the name Hera and the noun "kleos" meaning glory.

He is considered the greatest of the heroes of ancient Greek mythology, the most beloved and glorious. His myths acquired a pan-Hellenic character and are known all over the world. Hercules is a hero who was able to travel anywhere a man can imagine performing miraculous feats [5].

Hera was jealous of Zeus' infidelity with Alcmena and could not tolerate that Heracles was a young, successful hero, married and, in time, with three strong sons. Determined to kill the illegitimate son of Zeus, Hera sent two snakes to strangle the baby in his sleep. Hercules grabbed each snake by the throat and managed to strangle it just before they could strike.

Hera drove him mad and led him to commit heinous acts, murdering his family and close friends, and consequently, he was forced to become Eurystheus' servant [6].

In this paper, the path of Hercules through his twelve labors is explored and an attempt is made to highlight their symbolism, important for everyone's life. Methodologically, content analysis was used in material resulting from research in reliable magazines and websites on the Internet.

3. Hercules and the 12 labors

Hercules performed the 12 labors as he was forced to carry out Pythia's command, to serve his cousin Eurystheus, the son of a mortal, for 12 years. Thus, he obeyed what was asked of him trying to escape from evil, the fate he could not avoid (Kakridis, 1986:28). [4]

Hercules was a really strong man, with really big goals. Let's see his works:[7]

- The Nemean Lion: First Heracles had to bring Eurystheus the skin of the lion that terrorized the people. The lion lived in the hills of Nemea which is a city a few kilometers southwest of Corinth.
- The Lernaean Hydra: Hercules traveled to Lake Lerna where he encountered the Lernaean Hydra, an extremely venomous snake-like creature with nine heads that lived underwater, guarding the entrance to the Underworld. Lerna is a region in Argolis.
- The deer of Kyrenia: The hero had to capture the Kyrenia stag with the golden horns that were sacred to the goddess Artemis. The sacred deer lived on Mount Kyrenia in Achaia.
- The Boar of Erymanthos : Hercules was sent to catch a terrifying, man-eating wild boar. The boar lived on Mount Erymanthos in the Folois Gorge, in the area of Ancient Olympia.
- The Stables of Augeas: The hero had to clear all the manure from King Augeas' giant stables in one day. While this may sound simple, it was a huge and smelly task. Augeas was king of Elis, the ancient city-state of Ilia near the river Pinios.
- The Stymphalides hens: Hercules traveled to the city of Stymphalus and drove away the huge flock of birds that fed on human flesh. They inhabited Lake Stymphalia, a marshy lake in mountainous Corinthia, and destroyed the forests in the surrounding area.
- The Bull of Crete: Hercules traveled to Crete to bring the local king's bull to his cousin as the bull was terrorizing the island.
- The Horses of Diomedes: The hero traveled north to Thrace to capture the four wild horses of King Diomedes, who fed on human flesh [5].
- The Girdle of Hippolyta: Eurystheus commissioned Heracles to steal an armored belt that belonged to the queen of the Amazons, Hippolyte. The Amazons were a tribe of women who inhabited the Black Sea.
- The oxen of the giant Geryon: Hercules visited the Iberian Peninsula to steal the beautiful red oxen of the three-headed, six-legged monster Geryon.
- The Apples of the Hesperides: Eurystheus wanted Heracles to steal a row of golden apples - Hera's wedding gift to Zeus. To find the golden apples of the Hesperides, our hero crossed the river Iridanos - the river of ancient Athens and then the city of Tangiers.
- The Three-Headed Dog Cerberus in Hades: The final challenge led Hercules to Hades, where he had to kidnap Cerberus and bring him alive to Eurystheus. Cerberus was the vicious three-headed dog that guarded the gates to the underworld.

Basically, for 12 years, the story of Hercules was a long journey in many ways. To complete the twelve difficult tasks, Hercules displayed courage, strength, skill, and cunning, and had to almost die many, many times.

4. Emotional intelligence

4.1. Definition of Emotional Intelligence

There are several definitions of emotional intelligence since it is seen to be a multifaceted notion, depending on the area that researchers are attempting to address. Four themes are covered in her analysis: perception, comprehension, control, and emotional usage. [8].

Here are a few explanations:

- "Emotional intelligence is described as the capacity to regulate one's emotions, deal with emotional stress, and enhance one's skills in areas like creativity, art, and interpersonal communication.(Dictionary Greek)
- Salovey, Mayer, and others describe emotional intelligence as "a type of social intelligence, which includes the ability to monitor one's own and others' emotions, the ability to distinguish them, and the ability to use information from them to control one's thoughts and actions" [9].

"The capability of accurately processing emotional information related to recognizing, reproducing, and regulating emotions in ourselves and others" [10].

"The ability to perceive, express, and evaluate emotions, recall emotions when they facilitate thinking, understand and use emotional knowledge, and manage emotions to promote emotional and intellectual development" [11].

"A field of non-cognitive abilities, skills, and experiences that influence a person's ability to cope with the difficulties, pressures, and demands of their environment" [11].

- c) According to Goleman, emotional intelligence is "a group of abilities that refer to self-control, zeal, persistence, motivation, impulse control, restraint, managing moods, avoiding the influence of emotions on the thought process, hope and encouragement" [12].

Ability: "Knowing how you feel and being able to control those feelings before letting them "manage" you; being able to motivate yourself to achieve your goals; being creative; striving to the best of your abilities; understanding how others feel and being able to manage relationships with them; being able to give it your all in everything you do; and striving to be creative." [13].

"It's a combination of abilities that includes self-awareness, managing emotions, motivation, empathy, and social skills."

"Emotional intelligence is the capacity to control your mood, restrain your fervor, cope with disappointment, maintain optimism, and demonstrate empathy."

Other scientists and researchers describe emotional intelligence as "a person's capacity to recognize, accurately assess, and discriminate his own and others' emotions, to understand them, to 'assimilate' them in his mind, and to regulate both negative and positive emotions in himself and others." [14].

"Ability to appropriately intervene in others' emotional states and to direct others' emotional responses to various events" [15].

"A range of non-cognitive capacities, abilities, and skills that influence one's ability to successfully cope with environmental demands and pressures" [16].

"It's a kind of shrewd tactic that includes things like the capacity to remain composed under duress, foster an atmosphere of trust in your interpersonal interactions, be creative, and try to develop others." [17]

"The practice of observing your own emotions, as well as those of others, to give them importance and meaning, to process them, and to take them into account when it comes to receiving from phases" [18].

"The capacity to make the most intelligent use of our emotionality to support our interpersonal relationships" [19]. 4.2 The emotion [20] Biological responses in the body, mental states, and psychosomatic manifestations all combine to form the complex subjective conscious experience known as emotion.

Three fundamental components make up genuine emotion:

- The behavioral element/expression - in the face, the voice, and the body posture.
- The biological stimulation/effects on the body
- The cognitive element/justification - interpretation.

4.1.1. *The types of emotions*

The fundamental emotions, according to Goleman [21], are happiness, sorrow, anger, surprise, fear, and disgust.

Emotions are divided into:

- Negative emotions include melancholy, dislike, despair, agitation, misery, fury, hatred, and anger. Positive emotions include joy, compassion, enthusiasm, trust, admiration, happiness, and pleasure.
- The emotions of love, joy, fear, rage, jealousy, humiliation, and pleasure are examples of "simple" emotions. More "complex" emotions include those of gratitude, euphoria, malice, flattery, exhaustion, frustration, pain, boredom, betrayal, emotion, shock, etc. and
- the person's biological feelings, which are brought on by bodily processes like hunger, thirst, and satiety.

4.1.2. *The properties of emotions*

Emotions vary depending on:

- The intensity, which refers to how strongly, moderately, or minimally we feel an emotion.
- The characteristic that categorizes the mental state it induces into positive-pleasant and negative-unpleasant feelings, respectively.
- Their length is influenced by how long an emotion persists and the circumstances it may produce.

4.1.3. *Development - Recognition & Expression of Basic Emotions*

Humans experience a range of emotions from the time of birth until death. These feelings vary depending on the person's age and are expressed through appropriate emotional reactions.

People learn how to manage and communicate their emotions in a way that is acceptable to others. From an early age, children learn to identify their feelings and the means of exploring them with the assistance of their parents, who explain their own and other people's feelings. Of course, this comes before their analysis and identification.

Since it is a fundamental truth that emotions are a component of the nervous system and consequently cause the contraction of the 27 points of expression on the face—the eyebrows, forehead, eyes, nose, cheeks, and mouth—the investigation of emotions is done by the method of observing and differentiating the movements and contractions of the face.

[22] said that since emotions are present in all cultures, culture has a significant impact on how emotions develop. Children acquire an understanding of the "culture of emotions" (culture of emotions), including which emotions society permits expression and which do not. Thus, egocentric and heterocentric emotions are distinguished from one another.

Children often express four primary emotions: pleasure, sorrow, anger, and fear. In particular, laughter can be elicited by tactile stimuli (touch), by visual stimuli (facial grimaces), or by auditory stimuli (sounds). Expressions of joy (movements of the facial muscles, lips, and eyes, as well as glints of the eyes) can be observed from infancy onward.

Physical pain sensations, rejection, disappointment over the absence of a person or thing, and loss-related circumstances can all lead to feelings of sadness. Crying, wails, food or sleep difficulties, and evidence of connection to a particular person are some of the ways it is displayed. Anger is a negative feeling that children can sense from an early age and expresses itself when they experience pain, are attacked, or have their wants denied. One of the ways to convey anger is through aggression. Fear is one of the negative emotions, and it has a biological foundation. [23] When someone or something threatens them, they become insecure, which leads to fear. When someone is angry they attack yet when

they are afraid they escape. Fear may appear in many different ways, such as a nervous expression, shaking, yelling, approaching another person, etc. The stimuli's potency, unexpectedness, and danger determine a variety of reasons.

The following phases of cognitive and motor development [24] are when the link between emotional experience and expression of emotions changes:

- The growth of self-awareness: The capacity to view one's own image using the fundamental criteria of self-awareness, self-esteem, and self-regulation is a prerequisite for the development of a person's personality.
- Self-awareness: The understanding one has of oneself with a fundamental presumption of being aware of one's larger social context. Selman contends that regardless of an individual's cultural upbringing, the evolution of self-awareness occurs in relation to the individual's age, with each new piece of information that comes in creating an internal schema that is created by the same person as the new information he "provides" for himself every time.
- Self-esteem and self-concept: A person's conclusion about themselves is their level of self-esteem. refers to the perception of oneself that people form based on judgments and comparisons of their talents with others around them. Generally speaking, self-esteem is concerned with positives, weaknesses, emotional responses, and personality qualities. Self-concept, which James initially divided between two aspects of the self—"I" and "Me"—differs from self-esteem in that the former relates to the cognitive side of self-awareness while the latter refers to the emotional side of the person and the degree of self-evaluation. Age, the role played by the family, the school, the cultural setting, the person's gender, and their temperament are all important elements in the growth of self-concept [25].
- Self-regulation: According to [26], [27], "Emotional regulation covers all internal and extrinsic mechanisms that support the control, assessment, and change of emotions and in particular, their intensity and temporal aspects, to attain individual goals. The intersection of expressiveness, comprehension, and socialization is at the heart of emotional self-regulation [27]. Self-regulation is the capacity of the person to control his or her conduct on their own, in accordance with the situation. It is seen as a fundamental guarantee for the growth and evolution of the person, providing stability and moral autonomy. Self-regulation follows a developmental path and is shaped by the home environment. It results in both external and internal self-control, where parents first exert control over their children's conduct.

4.2. Theoretical Models of Emotional Intelligence [8]

Cognitive and emotional intelligence together with general intelligence make create a person's personality. Since emotional intelligence is hard to define, all theories for its interpretation treat it as a complex concept with numerous dimensions (abilities, characteristics, and skills) and references to various aspects of human nature (cognitive potential, personality, and behavior) [28]. Based on what these theories emphasize, the theories of emotional intelligence are categorized as follows:

- The models and theories are divided into three groups according to the first classification method:
 - Theories and models of ability: Emotional intelligence is seen as a mental capacity that, in terms of its composition and organization, corresponds with other forms of intelligence, which mostly pertain to cognitive capacities. Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso's representation theory.
 - Theories-models with a personality framework: the BarOn theory views emotional intelligence as a mix of personality traits and adaptability skills.
 - Theories and models of performance: Based on the Goleman theory, they attempt to both explain and forecast a person's effectiveness and performance at work.
- The models and theories are divided into two groups using the second method of classification:
 - Abilities are theoretically modeled using the Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso representative model. Competency models put a lot of emphasis on the capacity to handle emotional data and characterize emotional intelligence as a group of drive- and emotion-related skills.
 - Mixed theoretical models, which incorporate both achievement and personality-context models. A person's ability to successfully deal with environmental problems and demands, as well as their social and moral qualities, are determined by a mix of non-cognitive skills, personality characteristics, motivational variables, talents, and skills, according to models in this area of intelligence. Bar-on's model, Goleman's model, and Petrides and Furnham's model are examples of mixed models.

Mayer, Salovey & Caruso; b) Goleman; c) Baron; and d) The Pyramid of Emotional Intelligence: The Nine-Layer Model of Drigas & Papoutsis are briefly described below.

4.2.1. Theories of Ability - Theoretical model of ability: Mayer, Salovey & Caruso

Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso describe emotional intelligence as: "a type of social intelligence that involves the capacity to comprehend one's own and other people's emotions, to recognize nuanced distinctions between various emotions, and to use this information to steer his emotions. To reflect emotions or to feedback ideas and actions" [29].

In the current concept, each person's emotional "talent" refers to a meta-skill that defines how well they can use any skill they possess. Researchers [30] believe that emotional intelligence is a novel form of intelligence, which is supported by the results of their instrument, which assesses four distinct domains of intelligence. a) A person's capacity to perceive and identify their own emotions as well as those of others; b) their ability to integrate and assimilate emotions into their way of thinking (emotional facilitation of thinking); their capacity to process emotional information that influences their cognitive state and enriches their thinking process; c) managing emotions: the capacity to control one's own emotions as well as those of others by being able to accurately assess what is concealed behind the emotion and discovering/developing the appropriate ways to deal with emotions like fear, worry, anger, and sadness. Understanding emotions is the ability to comprehend complex emotions and emotional cascades, which leads to the improvement of interpersonal relationships.

According to Salovey, emotional intelligence is based on five primary axes:

- Understanding our emotions: Perceiving and recognizing our emotions is crucial for the growth of psychological insight and self-understanding.
- The capacity to manage and control our emotions, determining when they are acceptable at all times via self-awareness.
- Self-motivation: a quality that gives people the drive to achieve their objectives and be productive.
- Empathy, or the capacity to recognize another person's feelings, enables "empathic" persons to comprehend even the "silent social signals" of others around them.
- Communication with others is aided by relationship management, often known as the capacity to control other people's emotions.

4.2.2. Performance Theories - Goleman's Emotional Competence Theoretical Model

Emotional intelligence, as defined by Goleman as "the intelligence of the heart," is the capacity to find motivation within oneself, endure setbacks, restrain impulses, limit impatience, control one's mood, and avoid letting frustration stifle one's capacity for thought, empathy, and hope [12].

Goleman's theoretical model supports two types of intelligence: intellectual and emotional, highlighting that both types of intelligence reflect the activity of different brain centers. While emotional intelligence is based on the emotional centers located in deeper areas of the older subcortex [31] centers that work in coordination with the sp, intelligence is solely based on the functioning of the neural cortex, the most recently developed part of the brain.

Based on the foregoing, [13] contends that a person's path in life is determined by the balanced development of both types of intelligence. He emphasizes that, when emotional intelligence is not equally developed in a balanced way [32], intellectual intelligence does not guarantee success in people. He also contends that IQ tests and intelligence as a set of quantifiable cognitive talents only account for 20% of life achievement [28], with emotional intelligence accounting for the other 80%. This position is shared by other scientists [33],[34].

[32] Distinguishes four categories of emotionally acquired skills, each consisting of five emotional skills [28], highlighting the fact that our emotional intelligence dictates which skills we have and how well we can apply them based on five factors: self-awareness, behavioral motivation, self-regulation, empathy, and skill in interpersonal relationships. While the aforementioned traits are grouped together, they are all based on a single common core emotional intelligence dimension. We all have a profile of strengths and limitations since humans do not fully develop all of the aforementioned talents.

According to Coleman, the traits of emotional intelligence abilities include independence: each makes a unique contribution, interdependence: each influences others in some way while there is also strong interaction between them, and hierarchical connection: one builds on the other. Coleman also claims that emotional intelligence abilities are a necessity but not a skill because the existence of a fundamental ability does not ensure the development of a skill that is related. **Goleman theory model [7]**

Table 1 Goleman model: The Emotional Competence Framework. (Source: [30], [26])

	SELF	OTHERS
	PERSONAL CAPACITY	SOCIAL ABILITY
RECOGNITION OF EMOTIONS	SELF CONFIDENCE Emotional self-awareness Accurate self-assessment Self-confidence	SOCIAL AWARENESS - Empathy - Service orientation - Organizational awareness
REGULATION OF EMOTIONS	MANAGING SELF Self-control Reliability Conscientiousness Adaptability Achievement Motivation Initiative	RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT Development of others Influence Contact Conflict management Leadership ability A catalyst for change Create links Teamwork & cooperation

4.2.3. Mixed Model Theories or Models with a Personality Framework - m BAR-ON Theoretical Model: A Model for Emotional and Social Intelligence

According to Bar-On, a person's general intelligence—an indication that is likely to lead to success in life—is equal parts influenced by their emotional intelligence and intelligence. The [16] describes emotional intelligence as a complicated notion that is "a set of non-cognitive abilities, capacities, and skills that influence one's ability to successfully cope with environmental demands and pressures". A person with strong emotional and social intelligence, according to Bar-On's personality model, "can successfully deal with any changes that occur in their personal or social environment, adapt to circumstances, and solve any problems." In addition to having optimism and the capacity for self-motivation, he needs arrange his emotions in a way that serves him personally in order to accomplish the aforementioned. [35]

The model put out by [36] is divided into five categories, each of which has a set of particular talents [28], as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Goleman model: BAR-ON Theoretical Model: A Model for Emotional and Social Intelligence (Lykou, Manoli, Drigas, 2023)

1) Intrapersonal skills	a) emotional self-awareness b) assertive behavior c) self-respect d) confidence in personal abilities e) independence
2) Interpersonal skills	a) empathy: b) interpersonal relationships: c) social responsibility:
3) Adaptability	a) tolerance to stress b) impulse control

4) Stress management	a) problem-solving ability b) reality check c) flexibility
5) General disposition	a) happiness b) optimism

A second classification of the aforementioned skills into three hierarchically related categories is also offered by Bar-On, who emphasizes that the skills in the first category serve as the basis for the skills in the next category.

- Fundamental abilities: empathy and emotional self-awareness
- Supporting abilities: self-assurance in social abilities, optimism
- Problem-solving and establishing interpersonal connections as follow-up skills.

4.2.4. The Pyramid of Emotional Intelligence: THE NINE LEVEL MODEL

Figure 1 The Pyramid of Emotional Intelligence

The researchers [37] contend that the development of emotional intelligence in the nine-level model is based on interpersonal and interpersonal meanings concepts ([38], [39]) and incorporates elements from both constructs (the EI Ability model and the Trait EI model) into a more hierarchical structure.

The nine levels of the emotional intelligence pyramid:

- Recognizing and classifying every emotional stimuli in order to gauge emotional state.
- Perception-Recognition of Emotional Expression (Vocal or Non-Vocal)
- Complete awareness of our ideas, feelings, strengths, and flaws.
- Exercise self-control and self-regulation in order to manage both good and negative emotions.
- Social awareness, empathy, and emotional discrimination in understanding the thoughts, wants, and worries of others.
- Social skills, or emotional intelligence, are a requirement for socialization and the development of self-concept.
- Self-actualization, or realizing all of your potential skills and achieving them, is number seven.
- Transcendence - assisting others in realizing their potential and achieving self-actualization. transcending one's own self.
- Emotional Oneness - We are all emotionally bonded to one another, to the natural world, and to the entire planet.

Every individual strives throughout their lives to fully develop their personalities by mastering cognitive and emotional intelligence, managing their emotions, and cultivating their sense of worth, self-awareness, and self-control. Through his labors to achieve "purification" in self-realization and emotional unification, Hercules underwent the emotional "search" trip.

5. Emotions and symbols in the 12 labors of Hercules

The labors of Hercules are related to repentance, and the redirection of wild emotions, and can teach people through time.

In his first labor, Hercules' fight with the lion is based on his aggression, anger, and rage. Defeating the large and extremely fierce creature could not be done with arrows. [40] The hero had to muster both his courage and his amazing physical strength and at the same time constructively exploit his negative emotions - abundant aggression and anger - to get rid of the presence of evil. It experiences the full knowledge of emotions – their strengths and weaknesses, our thoughts, our beliefs, and their management [3 7].

This first mission was also the first step towards atonement. The struggle with the lion is seen as man's struggle with his ego and pride. Having completed his first mission, Hercules wears the opponent's skin as protective armor for his next trials, as he was immune to iron, stone, or wood. The act is also associated with ritual actions that were associated with purifications [41]. The slaying of the Nemean lion symbolizes the victory of the brave individual over the wild, the animal instincts of man through the power of his mind represent the strength of the unshakable will of the soul. For Hercules, completing this task was the first step toward atonement

In the second feat, Hercules traveled to Lake Lerna to defeat the Lernaean Hydra. That's why he had to think differently. Every time Hercules cut off a Hydra's head, two would grow in its place. Guided by Athena and aided by his friend Iolaus, our hero will eventually overcome the Lernaean Hydra, preventing the growth of new heads. After each decapitation, he cauterized the open wounds to prevent the birth of others [4 2]. As the central immortal head was his main opponent, to eliminate it he buried it under a huge stone. With this victory, Hercules feels even more empowered. After slaying the hideous Hydra, he turns his demonic toxicity into a power to use for his war of good against evil, as he dipped his arrows in the poisonous blood to help him face what comes next.

The Lernaean Hydra seems to be the darkness within us that cannot disappear forever from life. Desires that arise because of our ego may be limited or constantly under control. The toxic blood of the Lernaean Hydra symbolizes anger, which must be recognized and understood to be controlled. Lakes are generally believed to be an entrance to the Underworld. the lake of Lerna is mentioned as a place of purification for murder [4 3] this extermination it also symbolizes the victory over death [5].

Consequently, we need to behead our desires and burn them with the fire of our spirit/mind, a symbol of purification [40]. Our hero acquires skills such as adaptability – resistance to stress and impulse control according to the model [3 6].

For his third feat, the hero hunted the stag with the golden horns. It was a daring act as it was forbidden to touch it. When Artemis appeared before her our hero spoke kindly and promised to return the deer safe and sound to her forests. The goddess accepted. According to Pausanias, Hercules did not want to kill or injure the animal. So he followed it and caught it with nets either in sleep or because he tired it after a year's continuous pursuit [4 4] During the year's hunt, he found himself in the lands of Thrace and the Scythians, on the northern shores of the Black Sea. The deer was finally caught in Arcadia on the Ladon River. Golden horns symbolize higher knowledge. The deer is the intellect. Hercules in this work works without his muscular strength, displaying agility and mental prowess commensurate with his physical [4 5] and his discretion, so as not to offend the sensitivity of the goddess. Here the soul comes into contact with intuition, protection and care, feeling and affection. People need to be freed from their shackles and the ego that runs wild and out of control everywhere. This happens when the individual acquires higher knowledge/spirituality, self-awareness, self-control, and self-management. [35]

In the fourth labor, Heracles' mission was to capture the wild boar on Mount Erymanthos that was destroying the Spartans. No one had succeeded in killing it and those who tried met a tragic death. Eurystheus ordered Heracles to bring it alive to him in Tiryns. In this area, the hero found himself close to centaurs who do not like humans but also close to friends who hosted him. After a misunderstanding, Heracles kills his friend Pholos, wounds Chiron, and runs away [2]. Finally, he found the wild boar and managed to tie it with a noose.

During the hero's rest, where he was receiving hospitality and feasts with his friends, he lost his concentration and caused the death of his friends. Fun makes people lose balance power and wisdom from their lives. Due to extreme personal interests, a person easily becomes an aggressive boar, which can harm not only the natural environment but also the people around him [40]. Many times people try to use illegal means to achieve their goals based on their self-

interest. The development of social skills is required as a prerequisite for socialization and better social interactions and the formation of self-concept toward understanding and emotional unity [3 7].

The fifth mission was also the "dirtiest". Augeas' stables were very large. They housed a huge number of cattle and so the amount of dung that had never been cleaned before was very large and almost impossible to clean in one day [5]. The challenge required Hercules' abilities beyond muscle strength, such as intelligence, ingenuity, resourcefulness, and much more humility and recognition of his human limitations. With this feat, Hercules masters some of the key features of emotional intelligence, non-cognitive abilities, and skills that influence one's ability to successfully cope with environmental demands and pressures [1 6].

Despite the difficulties, he finally found a way to complete the mission. He cleared the stables in no time by diverting two rivers into the stables. The execution of an arrogant order [4 5] was designed to humiliate the hero. Many times in life we feel defeated by difficult events that make it clear to us that we are not completely in control of ourselves. Then we understand that we depend on higher forces deep within us. Their activation provides another attitude capable of approaching or even solving the problem in different ways. Every challenge must be faced with courage, no matter how stressful it may be for us. Procrastination does not help us deal with situations that trouble us. As time passes it reinforces what haunts us and makes it even more difficult for us. It takes small steps, focusing on the special features of each difficulty and looking for ways to solve it using our intelligence, creativity, and anger. Extrinsic motivation and reward can enhance our activation [40].

The stables of Augeas symbolize the corruption of an entire society, the corruption that for centuries abuses its power against its people, an era that brought to humanity slavery, human exploitation, and the loss of society's values. The river water that Hercules used to clean the stables symbolizes the cleansing power of water that can help bring awareness to the world.

The sixth labor required Heracles to kill the Stymphalian birds. He went to the lake where he could not see the birds. With the help of the goddess Athena and the two copper bells, they gave him. Hercules began to make a noise, and the birds were frightened and came out of their hiding places, so the hero killed as many as he could with the poisoned arrows [5]. Some were saved and flown to another place. The solution to this particular myth was given by Athena - the goddess of wisdom. When our thoughts trouble us, we need to get a sense of what's right, to separate right from wrong...and sometimes we need help to sort it out. Self-awareness and self-regulation are important skills of emotional intelligence [3 2].

In the seventh labor, Hercules finds in Crete the impressive and powerful bull, a gift from Poseidon to the king of Crete, Minos, to sacrifice for his sake. Minos, instead of sacrificing the bull, set it free on the island, causing great problems on the island.

Hercules, after chasing the animal all over Crete managed to ride it, they crossed the sea together and led it to Eurystheus. He saw the bull and, as Hera did not accept it as a gift, finally set it free [5]. The myth refers to the power of desire as the bull symbolizes our impulsive thoughts. Minos acted impulsively and led the place to destruction. Like the hero, we must try to control ourselves, to take charge of our impulsive thoughts and desires, to be able to balance both points and "stand" in the middle, gaining self-control and self-regulation of his emotions but even if he had social skills.

Hercules then went to Thrace to capture the four wild, man-eating horses of the giant king Diomedes [46]. In his duel with the hero, Diomedes ends up being killed by his horses. Completing the mission, the hero founded Abdera, which today is in the Prefecture of Xanthi. The city took its name from Abdiros, a friend of Hercules and son of Hermes, who was devoured by horses while helping his friend.

Horses symbolize the human mind, the birth, and conception of ideas. In addition, the tendency to adopt thoughts that can be destructive or constructive. It is, therefore, necessary for each person to be able to restrain his egocentrism, to recognize and tame instinctive impulses. Processes related to modifying one's reactions to achieve one's goals are recognized as elements of emotional regulation/self-regulation. [26], [27].

In short, the mares of Diomedes refer to the fact that if unbridled enthusiasm and impulsiveness are allowed to rise within man, due to success in life, the birth of a self-centered personality is imminent. something we must tame with the prudence of our personality.

Then the hero found himself in the land of the Amazons to take Hippolyta's girdle. The Amazons were a warrior race of women, autocephalous and warlike, famous for their skill with the bow and spear [5]. The Amazons loved Mars and rode horses. As our hero wanted to avoid war with them, he found the Amazons and asked Hippolyte for her girdle. The queen agreed to give it but the others reacted and rushed to Hercules with the signal of one of them - who was the goddess Hera. During the battle Hippolytus was killed and the others stopped the battle. Hercules took the girdle to deliver to Eurystheus. [2]

In myth, the belt symbolizes purity - physical and spiritual and also our respect for the different. Hercules a representative of the male gender invades the area where men were excluded. The queen being smart seeks understanding to avoid battle. However, Hera stirs up trouble and seeks battle. Hercules takes the belt through pain, death, and dissolution. The search for purity or oneness of spirit and soul requires patience, tolerance, data analysis, and research. Pure spirit is productive and helps every person to reach fulfillment. The hero adapts to the data and effectively copes with the changes in his environment to successfully solve any problems. To achieve this he needs to organize his emotions [3 5].

In the next labor, Hercules had to steal the beautiful oxen of Geryon, a giant with three bodies, three heads, and six arms based on two legs. His famous flock was guarded by a faithful shepherd and his terrible dog, which had two heads. The hero first used his strength and, reaching the place where the flock lived, killed both the dog and the shepherd. However, Geryon was not an easy opponent and Hercules used arrows dipped in the poison of the Lernaean Hydra and finally succeeded in taking the oxen [5]. Red beautiful oxen symbolize the lower desires, controlled by a shepherd (the mind) and a two-headed dog (matter and emotion). Hercules killed the bonds of his mind, matter, and psycho-emotional nature. Then he had to fight the monster of a man - Geryon, in all dimensions of existence - soul, spirit, body. Poisoned arrows are the means of purification. Thus the individual is freed from his lower nature and comes into contact with his soul.

Red cattle symbolize our hidden desires, focused on materialism, desires for which we are willing to do anything to achieve them, even if it means neglecting the needs of our spirit and soul. However, the combination of intrapersonal and interpersonal skills and flexibility and adaptability lead to the control of reality and the achievement of our goal [3 6].

In the penultimate mission, Hercules had to search for the golden apples at the edge of the known world where the Garden of Hera was [4 6]. He met with his vague answers the wise teacher of the seas Nereus, who led him to go south. On his way, he defeated the giant Antaeus (son of Poseidon and Gaia) and met Vouisiris (son of Poseidon and a mortal). Vouisiris persuaded Heracles, seduced him, and wanted to sacrifice him but the hero managed to overcome the obstacles in his way and escape. During his journey, Hercules met and helped Prometheus and Atlas. Atlas brought him the apples, which were guarded by a dragon and three maidens. Golden apples are many, a symbol of complexity, multiplicity, composition, and knowledge. In this search, there is always the element of fallacy and ambiguity.

Generally, apples symbolize knowledge and golden apples symbolize higher knowledge, the truth that makes man whole. However, only a few can attain this higher knowledge. and these few must have a heroic soul. The dragon and nymphs symbolize the guardians of this knowledge and prevent the uninitiated from claiming it and abusing it against humanity. The Realization of all potential abilities leads to self-actualization and Ego Transcendence, offering help to others to reach self-actualization, and to realize their potential. [3 7]

In the final mission, the hero was forced to visit the Underworld on a very different and difficult journey. He went to Cape Tainaro to find the entrance to Hades and Cerberus. He found the carnivorous Cerberus, the exceedingly merciless dog of Hades [4 7] with three dog heads and a serpent's tail standing at the entrance to the Underworld, terrorizing souls as they entered, barring the living from entering, and devouring those who wished to leave. On his way, he met and helped two tied men who were being attacked by animals. When Cerberus saw the hero, he was afraid and ran to hide under Pluto's throne. Pluto, at Persephone's urging, agreed to let Heracles take Cerberus if he could catch him. The hero fought and succeeded [2]

The dog with three heads is again the concept of the trinity - body, soul, and spirit. The tail of the serpent is the delusions and phobias that poison the spiritual life. Hercules climbs a mountain to find the entrance to the underworld, to enter the abodes of the soul. The three-headed Cerberus can be combined with the three necessary stages of preparation for entering the abode of mysteries: a) purification - liberation from the shackles of the material world, b) initiation - experience c) service to humanity. Along with the laborers, Hercules also helps other people who are suffering.

The soul does not forget that it is part of a whole. The hard struggle and victory of Cerberus - every material desire, pleasure, or fear, aims to rise to the summit of knowledge. Every man needs to face weaknesses before entering the abode of the temple of knowledge. If he enters with courage and confidence, like Hercules, the weaknesses - Cerberus will fear him. Personal experience is necessary for everyone and leads to the final destination: salvation and deification. THE Self-actualization – the realization of all possible abilities, the Transcendence of the Ego by offering help to others to reach self-actualization, and to realize their potential. They lead to Emotional Oneness - we are all interconnected with other people, with nature, and the entire planet. [37].

5.1. Hercules's journey to self-knowledge

Life is full of challenges. When we face difficult situations, we must think of our hero. Hercules remains a hero that everyone can relate to, precisely because his life was not perfect even though he had a god for a father. His daily struggles and relationships were not made any easier by his strength.

If Hercules could endure his sufferings, every man could survive. The 12 feats are the tests of our souls through achievements, difficulties, and obstacles so that each person can achieve perfection. It is our long journey to know ourselves, for our self-awareness.

When we overcome particularly difficult challenges in our lives - like Hercules in the 12 Labors - we gain from this experience confidence and courage that will serve us in all our future difficulties. Or as Nietzsche used to say: what doesn't kill you makes you stronger.

As time passes, we must behead our desires/inner demons and burn them with the fire of our spirit/mind, take control of our passions -2nd, 6th, 7th labors / REF ist ./ Taming our enthusiasm, hidden desires and ego leads us to use everything honestly, showing spiritual purity -3rd labor, and finding balance in our lives -7th, 8th, 10th labor. o The person must have patience, and tolerance, analyze the data and research the detail of the project, and think about every detail before making a decision - 9th feat.

It's not an easy case. Sometimes we need help to do this, as the goddess Athena did with Heracles -6th labor, to find our goal, avoid obstacles and reach higher knowledge -11th labor. We must control our interests -4th task, think of others around us and support them, be team-oriented rather than self-centered ways -4th task and try to clean our world, washing away all impurities -spiritual and mental, and bring back the values and the awakening of human consciousness -5th work.

Beating the monster within us and keeping our souls imprisoned in darkness is the final step to freeing our souls and becoming spiritually enlightened - the 12th feat. Then we have succeeded in the purification of our soul.

The world doesn't change if we don't change ourselves first!

Emotional intelligence is that "group of abilities that refer to self-control, zeal, persistence, motivation, impulse control, restraint, managing moods, avoiding the influence of emotions on the thought process, hope and encouragement" (Goleman, 1995) that will lead us to self-realization, to emotional unity.

6. Discussion on the role of ICTS in self-knowledge and Emotional Intelligence

Finally, we emphasize the significance of all digital technologies in the field of self-knowledge education and Emotional Intelligence training, which is highly effective, productive, facilitates and improves assessment, intervention, and educational procedures via mobile devices that bring educational activities everywhere [48-49], various ICTs applications that are the main supporters of education [50-61], and AI, STEM, and ROBOTICS that raise educational procedures to new performance levers [62-65] and friendly games [66]. Additionally, the development and integration of ICTs with theories and models of metacognition, mindfulness, meditation, and the cultivation of emotional intelligence [67-78], accelerates and improves more the educational practices and results, especially in emotional intelligence domain and its practices like assessment and intervention.

7. Conclusion

The life of Hercules through his myths followed the fortunes of Greek civilization and, overcoming the context of a local hero, took on global dimensions (Kakridis, 1986:18). His achievements transcended spatial contexts and are loved throughout the world and in modern times.

These myths received many analyzes and correlations basically on the path of every human being towards knowledge and through a constant struggle. They can show people great truths about their lives as everyone faces inner monsters, tasks, and tragedies that seem impossible to face.

Hercules, through the stories of his adventures, can inspire individuals to overcome challenges and embrace their heroic qualities. As he performed in the last mission, the last step is the ultimate revolution that we can bring about in the world we live in.

The glorious victory over ourselves: the revolution of consciousness, the revolution of the mind. If we change ourselves, our untrained selves, we will be able to gradually change the people around us... and in the long run the whole world. It is a serious mistake to try to change the world without, first, trying to change, improve, and empower ourselves in order to become operating in higher levels and reveal our higher abilities. Because only the self is your own enemy, only the Self is your own friend, The Self is your own friend when the mind is trained to use the executive functions and to operate the higher mental abilities, and not to be disturbed by the emotional disturbances of amygdala and the mammal part of the brain.

Compliance with ethical standards

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The Authors proclaim no conflict of interest.

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